

Minutes of the 64th Users' Meeting The Cosener's House, Abingdon, 4th February 2020

(This document was finalised on 17th July 2020)

Present:

(BB)	Dr Barbara Brooks ^{4,6}	
(DAH)	Dr David Hooper ^{1,4,5}	Secretary
(DK)	Dr Dirk Klugmann ⁵	
(EGN)	Dr Emily Norton ⁴	
(GV)	Prof Geraint Vaughan ^{4,7}	Chair
(GAP)	Dr Graham Parton ^{2,4,5}	
(HMAR)	Dr Hugo Ricketts ^{4,7}	
(HP)	Dr Hannah Price ^{3,4}	
(LD)	Mr Les Dean ¹	

Affiliation:

- ¹Capel Dewi Atmospheric Observatory (CDAO)
- ²Centre for Environmental Data Analysis (CEDA)
- ³Facility for Airborne Atmospheric Measurements (FAAM)
- ⁴National Centre for Atmospheric Science (NCAS)
- ⁵STFC Rutherford Appleton Laboratory (RAL)
- ⁶University of Leeds
- ⁷University of Manchester

Other abbreviations used in this document:

AMOF	Atmospheric Measurement and Observation Facility
DPW	Dave Wareing (University of Manchester technician)
MST(R)(F)	Mesosphere-Stratosphere-Troposphere (Radar) (Facility)
NERC	Natural Environment Research Council
RWP	Radar Wind Profiler
STFC	Science and Technology Facilities Council
UPS	Uninterruptable Power Supply
UTC	Universal Time

1. Minutes of the previous meeting

GV pointed out a that a rogue “p” in the penultimate paragraph of page 5 that suggested that LD was pouting: *LD pointed pout that the drainage system . . .* GAP pointed out that the name of the JASMIN computing system should be in uppercase.

2. Matters arising

ACTION ITEM 51.4.2 DAH to make the Met Office's model-comparison statistics for the MST radar permanently available to users if the Met Office will allow this.

COMPLETED

DAH reported that he now had access to the data, but that they had not yet been made publicly available.

GV recommended that the action should be considered to be completed and that DAH should speak to GAP regarding making the data available.

ACTION ITEM 64.2.1 DAH and GAP to make the Met Office's model-comparison statistics for the MST radar available through CEDA.

NEW

ACTION ITEM 60.2.1 DAH to extend the availability of the v4 Cardinal files back to the earliest date for which v3 Cartesian files are available.

ONGOING

DAH reported that had started to fill in the gap between June 2006 and May 2011. However, he had not gotten beyond October 2006. GV encouraged him to return to this since it was an easily achievable goal.

ACTION ITEM 61.3.1 DAH to introduce a mechanism to allow users to access data files that have not yet passed quality control checks and been delivered to the CEDA archives.

ONGOING

DAH reported that he had made some progress on this but that there was no solution in place. GAP reported that it was possible to create a web-accessible folder, which can be used even by people who do not have a JASMIN account. He recommended contacting Dan and James at NCAS for further details.

ACTION ITEM 62.2.1 DAH to make available the backlog of LD40 and WXT520 data in NCAS-approved files through CEDA.

ONGOING

DAH reported that his software was ready for this, but he still needed to discuss the implementation of NCAS data standards with BB. BB pointed out that a version 2 of the ceilometer standard was now available.

ACTION ITEM 62.2.2 DAH to make available machine-readable files to show the number of MST radar transmitters in operation at any one time.

ONGOING

DAH reported that no progress had been made on this.

ACTION ITEM 62.2.3 DAH to come up with a plan for creating version 4 MST radar data for dates when no version 3 files are available.

ONGOING

DAH reported that an over-arching issue was that he needed to adapt his data processing software to work with the latest Python software libraries. He had made a start on this by writing all new software in a way that is compatible with Python 3 as well as Python 2. GV acknowledged that this would be a big task, but highlighted the importance of DAH formulating a plan as to how he would tackle the problem.

ACTION ITEM 62.3.1 DAH and GAP to implement a consistent archive structure for the different versions of MST Radar data products files.

ONGOING

GAP reported that he didn't want to implement any name changes until it was clear what additional changes, if any, might be required as a result of the formation of the Atmospheric Measurement and Observation Facility (AMOF). Changing names will have implications e.g. for automatic backups of the archive. GV thought that the existing directory structure could be confusing for users who were trying to navigate the /badc/mst/data archive. GAP pointed out that it is now more common for users to discover datasets via web searchers rather than a systematic search of the archive structure and so the naming convention has less relevance than it used to be. Moreover, the catalogue pages clearly indicate when a newer version of a dataset is available.

ACTION ITEM 62.3.2 DAH and CJW to arrange for installation of the new MST radar transmitters, which will require help from additional members of Chilbolton staff, for the latter part of 2019.

ONGOING

DAH reported that ATRAD, the company responsible, had not been able to offer a suitable time period for this work. They had suggested to him in late November 2019 that they might be able to fit something in during the following month. However, this left DAH insufficient lead time to make arrangements. GV reminded DAH that the process of setting up a contract through NCAS would take time and so efforts should be made to initiate this as soon as possible. DAH reported that he was still having difficulties in finding an electrician to install the bespoke power connection required for the new radar equipment. If he could not find a local company who would accept a credit card payment, he would be obliged to rely on the Facilities Management procurement route, which is very slow.

ACTION ITEM 62.4.1 DAH to provide BB with a list of all of the instruments operated by the MSTRF and of all of the data products available. DAH should provide as much detail as possible.

COMPLETED

DAH reported this had been done.

ACTION ITEM 62.4.2 DAH to send BB details of raw LD40 data products so that the most appropriate way of storing them in netCDF files can be agreed.

COMPLETED

DAH reported that this had been done and that BB had suggested a way of recording the backscatter power product, which differs from that provided by other ceilometers.

ACTION ITEM 63.3.1 DAH to contact ATRAD in order to clarify the Uninterruptible Power Supply requirements for the new radar equipment

COMPLETED

DAH reported that ATRAD had confirmed that their equipment only provides a small Uninterruptible Power Supply (UPS) unit. This is used for the radar control and receiver units, but not for the transmitters. Since the transmitters are designed to be powered from a 3 phase supply, LD is building a system to distribute the site's single phase supply to each of the 3 phase inputs via a UPS unit. ATRAD have confirmed that this is acceptable. LD's system will cut the output of all 3 feeds if a single one is out of action. BB recommended using UPS units that allow the output power to be switched on and off remotely.

3. Facility Report - DAH

Full details of facility and instrument performance issues can be found at http://mst.nerc.ac.uk/cgi-bin/mstlog_public/mst_event_search.py.

3a) Data Management

DAH reported that the JASMIN system had been much more robust during the past 6 months than it had been during the 6 months covered by the previous Users' meeting. He had been pleasantly surprised that there had been no breaks in file transfers from Capel Dewi during the 10 days when the JASMIN system was left unattended over the Christmas/New Year period. GAP reported that the DAP server was experiencing ongoing problems. Although a temporary fix had alleviated some of these, others were ongoing. Files are typically indexed when they reach the CEDA archives. This allows for fast searches. However, some files are not being registered and so don't show up in web-accessed directory listings. GAP requested anyone encountering such issues to report them to CEDA so that they could be investigated.

3b) Electricity - DAH

DAH reported that shortly after the previous meeting he had resolved the issue of CEH accidentally paying a Capel Dewi electricity bill. The path of least resistance was for the CEH account holder to provide DAH with his password. This allowed DAH to log on to the CEH account and to pay the amount that CEH had previously been paid into the Capel Dewi account.

LD reported that in late October 2019 he accidentally discovered that the PowerPerfactor voltage optimisation unit had been out of operation for some time. The purpose of the unit is to step down the mains voltage from 240 V to 220 V. In principle this can lead to a reduction in electricity consumption, which is why NERC installed them at all of their sites. However, since the MST radar transmitters do not operate stably with a supply of 220 V, the UPS units step the supply back up to 240 V. LD only tested the voltage available within the bungalow because he was having difficulties stabilising one of the transmitters after its UPS unit was replaced. He was surprised that the bungalow supply was at 240 rather than 220 V. He suspects that the PowerPerfactor had tripped at some point in response to an input supply problem. It has now been reset. It turns out that the new UPS unit had been outputting 220 V by default and so LD changed that to 240 V on 30th October 2019. This stabilised the transmitter it was supplying.

DAH reported that there was now a large collection of old UPS batteries at the site. Since they are very heavy, he has not attempted to carry them back to RAL. However, he will need to arrange for them to be collected for disposal/recycling. DK suggested that it might be possible to dispose of them through the RAL's Estates department.

The power supply to the whole Capel Dewi area was cut on 20th November 2019 to allow the local distribution company to carry out scheduled maintenance on their infrastructure. All instruments at the site were powered down between 08:45 and 09:00 UTC. The electricity supply was resumed just before 15:00 and all instruments were back in operation by 16:30 UTC.

3c) Telecommunications

GV reported that Dave Wareing (DPW) had been experiencing very slow connection speeds for the Manchester network (on the "phone" line) and asked whether there was anything that could be done to improve it. DAH suspected that this was a result of DPW maintaining a permanent connection to his (i.e. DPW's) home sky camera when he was on site. He noted that transfer speed on the NCAS network drops noticeably every half hour when files are being uploaded to JAMIN. Moreover, DPW had recently reached his 50 GByte monthly download limit. DAH had offered to switch to a connection option with a higher monthly download limit, but DPW had turned this down.

DAH reported that it had taken some time for the "alarm" phone line to become active after he had switched billing from BT to the provider (KCOM) for the other two phone lines. However, it was now working and was being used for the NCAS network since it was faster than the "fax" line. DAH's primitive method of testing connection speed is to use the computer command "ping bbc.co.uk". This

typically has a return time of just over 20 ms for the “alarm” line, but 27 ms on the fax line. For reference, DAH typically sees a return time of just above 20 ms from his home, but around 2 ms from the RAL network.

LD asked if it was possible to get a newer computer for DPW to use at the site since DPW was making do with one of GV's old laptops. DAH reported that he was already in the process of getting a new desktop PC to replace LD's Windows 7 machine. He will deliver this to site on his next visit.

3d) Miscellaneous

GV emphasised that it was important to keep new willow growth under control after the major efforts required to cut it back in June 2019. DAH reported that he would ask the existing grass-cutter to carry out extra spraying during the 2020 season.

GV also asked whether any progress had been made with replacing the “chicken shacks” that house the primary MST Radar power splitters within the MST Radar antenna array. DAH reported that he had discussed this requirement with the company that had overseen the willow clearance. Although they had taken down details, he had heard nothing further. LD reported that he and DPW had given some thought about the best materials to use. He wondered whether breeze blocks for the walls and galvanised metal for the roof would be more durable than the plywood and tar paper used on the current shacks.

DAH pointed out that the title “NCAS Capel Dewi Atmospheric Observatory” (CDAO) should now be used instead of “NERC MST Radar Facility”. This is because the term “facility” may only be used to describe one of NERC's official facilities. The CDAO, together with the Chilbolton Atmospheric Observatory (CAO) is currently part of the short-lived NERC Facility for Atmospheric Radar Research (NFARR). As of 1st April 2020 both observatories will become part of the Atmospheric Measurement and Observation Facility (AMOF). DAH pointed out that he had needed to create a modified banner, which he was using for this meeting (and at the top of these minutes), for sky camera time-lapse videos that he released in December. He will stop using it from 1st April 2020.

DAH reported that he had submitted an application to take part in NERC's annual Public Engagement Showcase event to be held in Cardiff in July 2020. He has proposed giving a talk on how the Welsh landscape affects the winds through valley flows and mountain wave generation. This fits NERC's requirements that the material should be based on NERC funded science and have a Welsh angle. GV had previously suggested creating an exhibit for the National Eisteddfod, which will be held in Tregaron at the beginning of August 2020. However, he had decided that this would not be practical since it would require the exhibit to be staffed for an entire week.

4. NERC Instrument Report - DAH

Full details of facility and instrument performance issues can be found at http://mst.nerc.ac.uk/cgi-bin/mstlog_public/mst_event_search.py.

4a) Campbell Scientific surface met sensors

DAH demonstrated how he used the plots of backscatter power from the Vaisala LD40 ceilometer to identify a partial blockage of the tipping bucket rain gauge between 4th and 13th December 2019. Periods of precipitation are easily identifiable in the LD40 plots as long as the cloud base is significantly above ground level. There were some periods during early December when the tipping bucket continued to register rain after the LD40 indicated that it should have ceased. LD cleaned the inlet filter on 13th December. It had become clogged by a build up of slime.

4b) Campbell Scientific surface wind sensors

DAH reported that the power supply for the new logger had failed on 29th October 2019. Consequently

no data were collected for a month until a new power supply was installed on 29th November. However, the logger failed to transfer any data after this. DAH visited Frongoch during the 2nd week of January 2020 in order to investigate. It turns out that the logger had been gathering data, but the 3G modem had lost its settings. DAH was grateful for the fact that there is still a telephone in the Frongoch hut and that the telephone line is still active. This allowed him to get one of Campbell Scientific's engineers to talk him through the process of trouble-shooting the problem and then fixing it. DAH was initially unable to connect to the modem since his laptop unexpectedly did not natively have a driver for the USB to serial cable. Nevertheless, Alan Doo at Chilbolton was able to forward him a link to the manufacturer's website, which allowed DAH to successfully complete the task by the end of the day.

DAH noted that he had not had time to check how well the logger's internal was keeping time. It's still not clear whether it synchronises to an external reference when it is connected to the 3G network. BB pointed out that a way to avoid uncertainty with the clock's fidelity is to add a GPS sensor to the logger and to record its time stamp whenever the wind speed and direction are sampled. She also pointed out that a Raspberry Pi computer was more than capable of carrying out the logging task required at Frongoch.

DAH had not initially created NASA Ames data files when the new logger was installed on 4th June 2019. This was because he needed to write new software to recreate the old logger's method of producing 1 minute interval values based on the 1 s interval samples. However, he processed the backlog in November 2019 when someone contacted him to ask when the data would become available. In order to address the question of whether the long-running NASA Ames dataset should be continued, DAH had asked the requester whether he would be able to handle netCDF files. The requester admitted that he would struggle, although he had project partners who would be able to do so. GV acknowledged the need to continue providing NASA Ames files, since there are clearly a number of users who rely on them. DAH will make the 1 s interval samples available in netCDF files as a separate dataset. GAP pointed out that CEDA has software that is capable of outputting netCDF data to an ASCII file format. Both BB and GV thought that making plots of the latest data should be given a higher priority than creating new datasets and data products.

4c) Vaisala WXT520 surface met and wind sensors

The latest data are still not publicly available. Nevertheless, DAH uses the raw precipitation data to help establish whether or not the Campbell Scientific tipping bucket rain gauge is operating as expected.

BB pointed out that the WXT instruments can be configured to measure rain in "tipping bucket" mode, i.e. indicating the accumulation within a given fixed period. At present the WXT520 produces precipitation messages at 10 s intervals, but only during a precipitation event. BB plans to send DAH a couple of NCAS-standard present weather sensors to be used at Capel Dewi. This will make the data from different NCAS sites more homogeneous.

4d) Vaisala LD40 laser ceilometer

DAH mentioned that HMAR had installed the new Lufft ceilometer at Capel Dewi during the first weekend in January. HMAR will give further details in section 6a.

4e) Sky Cameras

DAH reported that he had released 5 new time-lapse videos during December 2019. These cover Cumulus humilis (<http://cedadocs.ceda.ac.uk/1454/>), Cumulus mediocris (<http://cedadocs.ceda.ac.uk/1456/>), Altocumulus fluctus (<http://cedadocs.ceda.ac.uk/1462/>), wave-like Asperitas feature (<http://cedadocs.ceda.ac.uk/1463/>), and Altocumulus undulatus (<http://cedadocs.ceda.ac.uk/1464/>).

4f) Noctilucent Cloud (NLC) Camera

There is nothing to report on this instrument for the last 6 months.

4g) MST Radar

During the past 6 months, DAH has labeled several v3 Cartesian and v4 Cardinal data files as containing suspect data. Some of the issues are associated with mountain wave activity in the lower stratosphere. They are confined to narrow time-latitude regions, within which the wind speeds are significantly faster than at adjacent times and altitudes. For the example seen on 23rd December 2019, the problem is more pronounced in v4 data than in v3 data. A different type of issue led to slightly elevated wind speeds between approximately 09:30 and 11:30 UTC at altitudes above 15 km on 7th August 2019. Although these do not look out of the ordinary by themselves, the fact that the associated aspect sensitivity is reduced indicates some form of contamination.

The most common problem over the past 6 months has been caused by an elevated noise floor. This does not contaminate the wind data, but leads to a reduction in useful altitude coverage. Consequently files affected by this issue are not labeled as suspect. It is evident from raised values in the plots of Vertical Beam signal power. In some cases, e.g. on 6th September, the reduction in useful altitude coverage can be mild and confined to a short period. However, the useful altitude coverage is reduced to just a few km in extreme cases, such as during the morning of 4th September 2019. The total lack of coverage during the afternoon was the result of LD disconnecting the transmitters in an attempt to isolate the problem. LD and DAH made numerous other attempts to isolate the problem, e.g. by disconnecting individual transmitters. In one case, on 10th September 2019, LD accidentally re-connected the the receiver In-Phase and Quadrature feeds the wrong way round, when he switched to the spare receiver in order to check whether the receiver could be the source of the problem. This caused a reversal in the measured wind direction. DAH spotted the problem the following day and LD switched the feeds. The raised noise floor problem became less frequent and less severe during October 2019 before becoming more frequent again during November 2019.

GV asked whether each antenna sector could be tested down to the level of individual quads. LD pointed out that each sector feeds a large number of antennas. The only way to isolate them individually would be to disconnect their cables one by one. LD is of the opinion that standing water within the antenna array is probably the cause of the problem.

No useful wind data are available for the period between 04:50 and 11:15 UTC on 17th January 2020. The phase-reference unit had blown its fuse as the result of the internal fan failing. This meant that although the transmitters were operating, the signals were not in phase.

5. Guest Instrument Report

EGN gave a report on the mobile Radar Wind Profiler (RWP). The cause of no data being transferred during June turned out to be someone else using the same IP address as the RWP for another computer. There were problems with the power tripping on 13th June 2019, which were thought to have been caused by the weather being so cold and wet. DPW put a heating unit in the equipment container. He also had to change a power supply unit.

The new Degreane contact Julien visited Capel Dewi to carry out a service on the radar during the summer of 2019. The antenna had become very dirty, largely because of leaves falling from the nearby willow tree, which has grown large enough to start overhanging the RWP.

There was a problem with the Nyquist velocity automatically adapting to strong wind conditions on 11th July 2019. However, this issue appears to have finally been solved. There was a problem with incorrect winds during several days in November 2019. EGN wondered if this was caused by contaminating reflections from migrating birds. The problem was sometimes seen in the mornings, but mainly in the evenings.

EGN has found it difficult to send wind-profile data to E-Profile via the Met Office's data hub. Although she can carry out file transfers manually, her scripts are failing to run automatically.

BB asked about the ceilometer that is supposed to accompany the RWP. GV explained that it had been left at Cardington since there was already a ceilometer in operation at Capel Dewi. It had originally been planned to mount the ceilometer on the RWP trailer. However, it was thought that this might have an undesirable effect on the weight distribution.

EGN reported that she is now releasing data in netCDF files, which she hopes are compliant with the NCAS data standards. She started to use this for data collected during its current deployment at Capel Dewi.

GAP explained that CEDA treats RWP data from each deployment as a distinct dataset. Even if there are problems with the contents of the files, they cannot be removed from the archive (in case someone has made use of them in a publication). If revisions have to be made, the revised files will sit alongside the original ones within the archive. EGN had had problems with some files being incomplete, for example containing only a single profile. She will need to issue revisions for such files.

HMAR reported that the Elight lidar had been working well until the day before the meeting, i.e. 3rd February 2020. The Lufft ceilometer, which was installed in January 2020, is currently currently regarded as a guest instrument whilst it undergoes commissioning. However, when that is complete, it will become a CDAO instrument. More details are given in HMAR's presentation in the following section.

GV reported that there are problems with the SAOZ ozone-measuring instrument. It had been fine until an update of the GPS receiver was carried out in May 2019. The instrument has not worked since the GPS module was replaced in August 2019. It will have to be sent back to the manufacturer in France. Since the instrument has no official funding, there might be limited opportunities for carrying out repairs.

6. Science and technical presentations

6a) New Lufft ceilometer at the Capel Dewi Atmospheric Observatory- a first look (HMAR)

With help from GV, LD, and DPW, it only took HMAR half an hour to install the new instrument (a CHM 15k Nimbus) at Capel Dewi. The laser operates at 1064 nm and is within the eye-say 1M class. The 15k in the instrument name implies that it can nominally see up to 15 km. It is currently sampling at range intervals of 15 m (it can go down to 5 m) and at time intervals of 15 s (it can go down to 2 s). In principle, it can identify up to 9 cloud layers. Although the overall patterns seen by the Lufft and the existing Vaisala LD40 are similar, the Lufft is better at detecting cloud layers at the higher altitudes. HMAR thought that it was better at identifying the cloud base than the LD40. Moreover, it can identify the top of the boundary layer. Multiple aerosol layers can be seen on some days.

BB asked whether the instrument would be user configurable. HMAR said that in principle it could be, although this would depend on the long term measurement strategy. GV clarified that the instrument would be handed over to the CDAO once it had been commissioned.

BB asked whether it would be possible to run alternative cloud detection algorithms on the backscatter profiles. HMAR clarified that the E-PROFILE programme, which collects near-real-time ceilometer data for assimilation by weather forecasting agencies, run their own algorithms. GV didn't think that algorithm development would be trivial and so thought it best left to those who are already working on them.

GAP asked whether E-PROFILE planned to produce ceilometer files covering whole days. The data

provided to CEDA currently only cover 15 minutes, which means that there are lots of them. This is causing storage issues for CEDA.

6b) FAAM flight over Capel Dewi (HP)

The Facility for Airborne Atmospheric Measurements (FAAM) aircraft carries several humidity sensors and has the ability to deploy dropsondes. For the past 10 years FAAM has used only one model of dropsonde - the Vaisala RD94. However, it will move over to using the new RD41.

FAAM has known about a dry bias in the dropsonde humidity data for about 10 years. The manufacturer thinks the problem might be a result of the fact that the dropsondes have been in storage for a long time. Apparently the warm conditions in which they have been kept is the worst possible environment (BB suggested that chemicals from the packaging materials could have settled on the sensor). There is a method of preconditioning the sondes in order to counter the problem.

In order to compare the different measurements, the FAAM aircraft will overfly the Capel Dewi site, where humidity profiles will be measured by the Raman lidar. RS41 radiosondes will also be launched from the site. The highest flight level will be determined by the humidity profile on the day. The dropsondes will include an RD94 that has not been pre-conditioned, an RD94 that has been, and a RD41. The aircraft will remain at altitude until the sun sets (the lidar observations cannot be made during daylight conditions), before stepping down through flight levels and stepping back up. Dropsondes will be deployed again when the aircraft returns to altitude. The FAAM aircraft is capable of tracking up to 8 dropsondes, which can be launched at intervals of 30 s.

GV commented that he had performed a similar comparison in 2009. He only used one dropsonde and had not noticed any dry bias.

6c) A novel wind profiler (WP) design (DK)

This presentation covers DK's proof of concept for a novel WP design. It will use frequency modulated continuous wave (FMCW) rather than pulsed transmissions. It will be fully digital, using the software designed radio principle, and will make use solid state transmitter components. A high power gallium nitride power amplifier is available. The potential operating frequencies are 460, 960, and 1300 MHz. The direct digital synthesiser chip is only capable of generating frequencies of up to 600 MHz and so would need to be upscaled for operations at the higher frequencies. Beam steering would be achieved by digital beam forming rather than with hardware-based steering units. The original idea was to use the natural motion of a ship platform in order to vary the beam pointing direction. However, since there is currently no suitable processing scheme in place, this would require significant development work. Another option is to mount it on the back of a weather radar dish, which would already be steered. The antenna would probably be composed of 4 or 9 Yagis, which would be 4 m tall.

There is a cost balance between a cheaper/less-capable system and a more-expensive/more-versatile system. On balance it might be better to spend more so as to avoid technical issues in the future. DK started to develop this concept for a cloud radar, which never got built. The same principles would be appropriate for a wind-profiling radar. The project would need funding in order to develop it to a level suitable for a test deployment. BB suggested that NERC and British Antarctic Survey ships can carry container-sized deployments and so might provide an opportunity.

6d) CDAO ideas for the future (BB)

BB presented her ideas for how the Capel Dewi site could be developed in order to increase its visibility and the usage of the site and its data products. Potential new science areas that could be addressed include boundary layer, valley flows, and fog formation. A 10 m tower at the site could be used for a number of standard and novel sensors. She recommended including NCAS branded signage and an information board at the main gate (GV pointed out that these would need to be in Welsh as well as in

English). It would be good to improve links with Aberystwyth University, since the site offers opportunities for both teaching and research. Links could be formed with local schools and improving the supply of real time data plots would be welcomed by weather enthusiasts.

Hardstanding areas for instruments should have easy access to power (at both 110 V and 240 V) and data connections. Wireless data links could be used where wired connections are not practical. Within the building, UPS units should have the capability to have their output switched on and off remotely. It would be good if the internet connection could be improved. GV pointed out that although nearby University buildings have faster connections, it would probably be prohibitively expensive to get a dedicated fast link to the radar site.

GV suggested that if the next Users' meeting were held in Aberystwyth, interested members of the University's staff could be invited to attend.

6e) Raikoke eruption (GV)

The volcano Raikoke in the Kuril Islands (north-west Pacific) erupted on 22nd June 2019. A large plume of ash and sulphur dioxide was injected into the stratosphere, reaching an altitude of 17 km (according to measurements made by the CALIPSO satellite). Data from the TROPMI instrument on the Sentinel 5 satellite show that the sulphur dioxide initially circulated in a broad region around the source location, but didn't otherwise disperse. Eight day forward trajectories calculated by the NOAA HYSPLIT model show the same circulatory patterns at 13, 15, and 17 km. Eastward transport starts to become evident at 17 km for a model run initiated on 30th June.

Particles from the eruption were detected at Capel Dewi using a 355 nm lidar system with elastic and Raman channels. The elastic channel was configured for stratospheric measurements, allowing observations to be made up to 30 km. Radiosonde measurements are required to calculate the expected molecular (i.e. aerosol-free) backscatter profile. The presence of aerosols is indicated by a (observed to molecular) backscatter ratio of greater than 1. The Raman channel is very noisy at stratospheric altitudes since the short summer nights do not allow for long integrations. Nevertheless, the ratio of elastic to Raman signals can be used to confirm the presence of aerosols.

Aerosols detected at the end of June at around 14 km were probably from pyrocumulus clouds generated by forest fires in Canada. The backscatter ratio jumped up from 1.04 to 1.28 between 1st and 3rd July. These larger values are typical of volcanic ash, although the trajectories suggest that air from Raikoke should not have reached the British Isles this soon. The source of these aerosols remains unknown.

GV is more confident that Raikoke was the source of a thick layer of aerosol seen between the tropopause and 15 km on 13th July. The longer term measurements show the expected gradual decrease in the optical depth during the autumn of 2019. He is still uncertain how aerosol layers came to be seen at around 20 km since the eruption only reached to 17 km. Based on a time series in a paper by Trickl et al. (<https://www.atmos-chem-phys.net/13/5205/2013/>) this eruption has proved to be the most significant since Pinatubo in 1991 in terms of the integrated particle backscatter coefficient.

7. Any Other Business

GV stated that fixing the problems with the Frongoch data feed should be the top priority. Releasing data from the LD40 and WXT520 should be the next priority. DAH should have a plan for the MST radar hardware installation by the next meeting. Keeping the willow growth under control is an important longer term requirement. Action needs to be taken to deal with the MST Radar noise floor issue.

DAH should look into the possibility of holding the next meeting in Aberystwyth. It could be wrapped around the afternoon of one day and into the following morning. GV suggested 17th/18th June 2020 as a potential slot.